

LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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ANNOTATION

This article talks about how to acquire a second foreign language. And the opinions of several scientists are analyzed.

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In the last three decades, many experts have conducted research on second language learning and various hypotheses have been put forward. Among these various theories, S. Krashen's "Monitor Model", proposed in the 1980s, has gained wide popularity and influence in the field of second language acquisition teaching and research, and this theory has been enriched and refined over time in a number of his works (Krashen, 1981; 1982; 1985). ; Krashen and Terrell, 1988). The main components of Krashen's monitor model are five interrelated hypotheses: the acquisition-learning hypothesis, the monitor hypothesis, the natural order hypothesis, the input hypothesis, and the affective filter hypothesis, which are discussed in depth. Despite its popularity and importance, it is often the subject of criticism and controversy. In this article, we will critically evaluate Krashen's Monitor Model and assess its advantages and disadvantages in second language learning. Learning, the opposite of acquisition, is a 'conscious and explicit' process concerned with 'knowledge of language', 'rules' or 'grammar' (Krashen) (Krashen & Terrell, 1988, 26-27 pages). & Terrell 1988) and this involves deliberate practice and recall. According to Krashen, learning cannot become mastery and there is "no interface" between mastery and learning.

Closely related to the Acquisition-Learning hypothesis is the Monitor Theory, which aims to explain how learning and acquisition are applied and includes a natural

interaction between the two. Monitoring "provides an awareness of what is being produced, allowing for the pre- or post-examination of many language slips, grammatical errors, social deficits, and other deviations from the goals that define normal speech" (Morrison & Low). . , 1983, p. 228, cited in Ellis, 1994).

Krashen's theory of SLA was originally called Monitor Theory because the Monitor Hypothesis formed its basis. There are two ways to build skills in a second language; one of them, acquisition, is automatic and unconscious, as I said earlier in the section on the learning/acquisition distinction hypothesis. Krashen said that procurement is responsible for preparing the statements. The monitor, the knowledge storage area, will eventually correct these claims. According to Abuhattala, I. (2013), this hypothesis considers three different categories of monitor users: (1) Over-observant users or those who often do not trust their acquired skills and check every sentence using it 'students. Such speakers, of course, speak slowly and incoherently. (2) Controlled users, or speakers who focus primarily on meaning rather than accuracy, are at the other extreme. Even when speaking in their native language, these speakers are often animated, and while they make more mistakes than hyperobservant users, they tend to say more meaningful things. (3) Optimum monitor users or owners who manage to use the monitor only when necessary, such as when speaking or writing letters. Because they use acquired competences as well as acquired competences, and in many cases can use logically modified L1 grammar to speak English with a monitor, optimal monitor users are generally more self-sufficient than under-monitor users. they give the impression that they are qualified. same purchase level. This Krashen refers to the L1 + monitor mode. The fact that the communication process has already been formed gives the speaker additional information, which is one of its advantages. (Abuhattala, I. (2013). Much research on the acquisition process, particularly research on first language acquisition, is production-based. McLaughlin also points out that "fair use" is not a rigid standard; even for grammatical morphemes, it is not always necessary to use them in the same way. Overall, we can conclude that Krashen's Monitor model can be a very systematic and comprehensive theory, supporting our

contributions such as criticisms of Krashen's monitor model in the field of second language acquisition. Years of observation, analysis and teaching. The most popular theory in second language acquisition, it covers almost every aspect of second language acquisition during this Monitor model. It seems that he is trying to explain the excess throughout this single model, which is additionally one of the sources of the theory's shortcomings, as we all know that it is very difficult to claim any variable under consideration in second language acquisition. A time. Although the lack of empirical evidence or the vague definition of terms did not have the opportunity to test some of the hypotheses in his theory in some sense, these shortcomings forced various researchers in the field of second language acquisition to come back with higher solutions to the problems found. . in addition, it is a driving force for accelerating theories in second language acquisition. In any case, we have a tendency to overlook the importance of his theory simply because of its flaws. In addition, this theory plays an important role in second language teaching all over the world and some effective teaching methods support the main claims of its theory to help students acquire a second language better. Despite various criticisms of all views, Krashen's Monitor model has played a major role in the field of second language acquisition and second language teaching.

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